

**Facilitating polymer property prediction with machine learning and Group
Interaction Modelling methods**

Elaheh Kazemi-Khasragh^{1,2}, Juan P. Fernández Blázquez², David Garoz³, Carlos
González^{1,2}, Maciej Haranczyk^{2, *}

¹ *Departamento de Ciencia de Materiales, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, E.T.S.
de Ingenieros de Caminos, 28040 Madrid, Spain*

² *IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel 2, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain*

³ *Instituto de Fusión Nuclear - Guillermo Velarde, Polytechnic University of Madrid,
28006, Madrid, Spain*

** Corresponding author: Maciej Haranczyk*

Email: maciej.haranczyk@imdea.org

Abstract

Identification of a suitable polymer material for a given applications requires information about the properties and behavior of the material, which is time-consuming and costly to measure experimentally. In this study, we explore two computational alternatives; namely, Group Interaction Modelling (GIM) and Machine Learning (ML) approaches, as two avenues for predicting six different thermal and mechanical properties of polymers. Random Forest (RF) was employed as ML algorithm. Molecular descriptors for ML and physical input parameters for GIM method were obtained directly from the chemical structure information of polymers. The ML models developed in this study exhibited strong predictive performance, achieving R^2 values ranging from 0.83 to 0.955 across the evaluated properties. The accuracy of the ML and GIM method has been compared with each other, and the evaluation is demonstrated that ML approach offers more reliable predictions over the GIM method. Furthermore, we found that the accuracy of the GIM predictions was highly dependent on the accuracy of the Debye temperature values used as an input parameter, particularly for predicting the glass transition temperature. Therefore, for better prediction in GIM procedure, it is essential to use accurate techniques to find the Debye temperature values.

Keywords: Polymer materials, Group interaction modelling, Machine learning, Thermal and mechanical properties.

1. Introduction

Polymeric materials have been successfully employed in a wide spectrum of applications that virtually encompass every human life. The increasing need for higher strength, lower weight and smaller environmental impact have fueled the search for new polymers as well as (re)-assessment of already applied materials (Khan and Roy 2018). In each case the properties and behaviors of any candidate material need to be measured, which is costly. Computational approaches have provided an alternative.

Polymeric materials possess a hierarchical structure that spans multiple length scales, ranging from the molecular level to macroscopic dimensions. At the molecular level, properties like bond lengths and angles, as well as torsional angles, dictate the structural stability of polymer chains. Moving up the scale, interactions between chains, such as van der Waals forces and intermolecular bonding, impact mechanical strength, elasticity, and thermal conductivity. The mesoscale involves the arrangement of chains and the formation of domains, influencing properties like crystallinity, phase separation, and permeability. Finally, at the macroscale, factors such as shape, dimensions, and processing conditions affect properties such as tensile strength, impact resistance, and optical transparency. To fully comprehend polymeric materials and alleviate the experimental burden, it is crucial to develop a multiscale modeling approach that accurately captures the interplay between these length scales and associated material properties (Li et al. 2013; Boso and Schrefler 2009; Gooneie, Schuschnigg, and Holzer 2017; M Chanda 2013). Multiscale modeling concerns the derivation of equations, parameters, or simulation algorithms that describe behavior at a given length scale based on the physics at a finer scale. Multiscale modeling, which may involve quantum mechanics and, molecular dynamics (thermodynamics, crystalline structure, defect interactions), computational thermodynamics (phase diagrams), and phase-field

modeling (phase transformation and microstructure development), is a powerful technique for capturing information at different levels of detail (Fish, Wagner, and Ketten 2021)(Llorca et al. 2011).

Although multiscale modeling can provide atom level understanding of the observed properties, it requires long simulations and complex algorithms to assemble the models across scales. Hence, it is not ideally suited for exploring large number of materials. There are, however, two alternative approaches based on either a simpler physical model or data-driven approach where structure-property relationships are recovered from data via machine learning.

The first approach to predicting material properties is based on defining parameters from the microstructure, and then using a semi-empirical expression based on these parameters to calculate the properties. This method is called Group Interaction Modelling (GIM), as a microscale framework estimates engineering and thermomechanical properties of desired polymers as a function of temperature and strain rate (J. P. Foreman et al. 2012; J. Foreman and Foreman 2016).

The GIM method is particularly useful in the initial steps of designing new polymers due to its speed, cost-effectiveness, and ability to fill in gaps where experimental techniques are problematic such as experiments at temperatures lower than 25 °C. In addition, the method's meticulous physical basis allows user to calculate numerous significant properties of the materials that would not be easy to measure otherwise. For instance, GIM can be used to predict the glass transition temperature, heat capacity, linear thermal expansion, elastic modulus, and Poisson's ratio, among other properties (J. P. Foreman et al. 2010).

This framework, introduced by Porter (David Porter 1995) was initially devoted to predicting linear polymers' properties. However, the method can be used to predict the

mechanical behavior of polymer networks such as epoxy resins. Application of GIM technique to predict the properties of the epoxy resins needs some modification to the original method of Porter because the interaction of the atoms in the crosslinked polymer is different compared with the linear polymers. For this reason, the degrees of freedom, N , as an important parameter in GIM method were evaluated, and the incorporation of the resin crosslinking was shown by decreasing the value of N by three for each trifunctional branching site on the monomers (Joel P. Foreman et al. 2008). By this modification, Guest et al. (Guest et al. 2013) calculated the glass transition temperature (T_g) and stress-strain curves of the epoxy system and compared them with the results of the experimental tests. Although the prediction values of T_g have good agreement with experimental values, the predicted stress-strain curves do not fit well with the experimental results. Besides applying the GIM method to predict the mechanical properties of the polymer materials (Porter and Gould 2009; J. P. Foreman et al. 2012; Joel P Foreman et al. 2006), this method was used in few studies to predict the properties of the polymer composites (J. P. Foreman et al. 2009; 2010) which are based on epoxy systems.

Although this prediction can help make quick decisions about the suitability of polymers for specific applications, there are difficulties involved. One main challenge is obtaining input parameters for the studied polymer. Some parameters can be determined using tables of group interaction based on the monomer structure, but others require experimental results or advanced simulations. For example, the Debye temperature requires studying the polymeric structure with atomistic codes that describe electronic configuration and atomic displacements.

The alternative approach is to employ Machine Learning (ML) techniques (Liu et al. 2020; Guo et al. 2021). Yu et al. (Yu et al. 2006; Yu and Huang 2017) utilized multiple linear

stepwise and artificial neural networks to predict the T_g of polystyrenes, addressing the long-standing need for reliable T_g estimations. Furthermore, the application of Gaussian process regression (Le 2020) successfully unveiled predictions of tensile strength for polymer carbon nanotube composites, presenting a breakthrough in the field of advanced polymer composites. These remarkable achievements, along with the successful utilization of neural networks (X. Wang 2008), support vector regression (Pei et al. 2012), and artificial neural networks (Velten, Reinicke, and Friedrich 2000) in accurately predicting T_g, tribological properties, and other mechanical characteristics, highlight the immense potential of machine learning methods in addressing the complex challenges of polymer property prediction. Moreover, exploring the prediction of electronic, dielectric, storage modulus, damping, and specific heat capacity properties of diverse polymers through machine learning approaches (Mannodi-Kanakkithodi, Pilia, and Ramprasad 2016; 2002; Bhowmik et al. 2021) opens up new avenues for advancing material design and engineering. These collective efforts showcase the effectiveness and promise of machine learning in unlocking the vast possibilities of polymer property prediction.

Our study seeks to combine machine learning (ML) and simple numerical models to predict the mechanical and thermal properties of polymers, eliminating the need for complex modeling techniques such as molecular dynamics. By adopting a data-driven approach, we offer a more efficient and reliable method for predicting polymer properties, which significantly speeds up the material selection process.

The primary focus of our research was to compare the accuracy and reliability of ML and Group Interaction Modeling (GIM) methods in predicting six different thermal and mechanical properties of polymers. This comparative analysis has wide-ranging industrial applications that heavily rely on precise knowledge of polymer properties for optimal material selection and design. Our findings underscore the importance of

leveraging advanced computational techniques to ensure accurate parameter inputs that enhance the predictive capabilities of models in the field of polymer materials.

2. Methods and methodology

In this paper, the theoretical framework of GIM method is first introduced and the equations for predicting polymer properties based on molecular interactions are described. Then ML algorithms for predicting polymer properties are explained and their strengths and limitations are discussed. Finally, our methodology, which leverages the strengths of both GIM and ML algorithms to achieve more accurate predictions of polymer properties, is presented.

2.1. Group Interaction Modelling: The model framework

The Group Interaction Modelling (GIM) technique is employed to forecast the thermal, volumetric, and mechanical properties of polymers through the utilization of a mean-field potential function. By employing a contribution-based methodology, the GIM method computes the total energy of the system. The interactions between adjacent polymer chains are described by a potential function comprising various thermodynamic energy terms. This thermodynamic potential function serves as the equation of state for the system, as illustrated in Eq. (1) (J. Foreman and Foreman 2016; J. P. Foreman et al. 2010).

$$E_{\text{total}} = \phi_0 \left[\left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right)^6 - 2 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right)^3 \right] = H_M + H_T + H_c - E_{\text{coh}} = -0.89E_{\text{coh}} + H_T \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

The potential energy is based on a standard Lennard-Jones potential function where the cohesive energy E_{coh} is the molar quantity of the molecular potential well depth ϕ_0 , V_0

is the volume with zero potential, and V is de volume. Also, the E_{total} contains mechanical H_M , thermal H_T , configurational contributions H_C and cohesive energy E_{coh} . In the context of GIM techniques, the term H_M refers to the energy associated with mechanical deformation per interaction. H_T is based upon the molecular level temperature changes through heat capacity ($H_T = \int_0^T C_{V,\text{skeletal}} dT$, which $C_{V,\text{skeletal}}$ is heat capacity contributed by skeletal vibration). H_C was estimated by the level of the cohesive energy for different conformations. The energy equation (Eq. (1)) was used by GIM system to develop calculations to predict the structural properties of polymers. For this purpose, numerous parameters based on the representative mer unit were used as input parameters of GIM method. The input parameters of GIM method are represented in Table 1 (J. P. Foreman et al. 2009; Porter and Gould 2009; J. P. Foreman et al. 2012; J. Foreman and Foreman 2016; J. Foreman 2020; Joel P. Foreman et al. 2008; 2010).

Table 1. Input parameters of GIM method

Parameter	Description	units
M	Molecular weight of mer unit	g/mol
V_w	Van der Waals volume of mer unit	m^3/mol
E_{coh}	Cohesive energy	J/mol
N	degree of freedom	Mer unit ⁻¹
θ_1	Debye temperature	K
θ_E	Einstein temperature	K
L	Length of a mer unit in the chain axis	m or Å

The monomers' molecular weight, Van der Waals volume, Cohesive energy, and freedom degree can be calculated with the group contribution method. Each repeating unit in the chain of the polymers contains several functional groups, and the information of each functional group is tabulated in Ref. (David Porter 1995) (J. P. Foreman et al. 2009). The other three parameters (the length of the monomer, Debye, and Einstein temperature) can be obtained via molecular modeling. Once the molecular structure is generated, the length of each mer unit can be measured from the coordinates of atoms. The length of the monomer was calculated using the Avogadro program, which is a molecule editor and visualizer (Hanwell et al. 2012). After designing the molecules of the polymers with the support of Avogadro program, the geometry of the molecule was optimized, and the length of each monomer was measured.

Debye temperature and Einstein temperature are related to the vibration of atoms in the structure, and can be predicted using electronic structure methods. Debye temperature, which is the maximum temperature related to the single normal vibration, can be estimated with the skeletal vibration. Note that the skeletal vibration is transmitted to the entire material. Einstein temperature (θ_E) is estimated by Group vibration (David Porter 1995). The vibrational frequencies of several polymers have been computed by density-functional theory (DFT) at gas-phase conditions. A functional of CAM-B3LYP was applied with the basis of 6-311++G** (Yamamoto et al. 2017) to the polymer trimers. The calculation was performed by Gaussian 16 program (M. J. Frisch et al. 2016).

In Gaussian, to calculate the vibration mode, second derivatives of the energy with respect to the Cartesian nuclear coordinates are determined. The necessary force constants to determine the frequencies are on Hessian matrix diagonalization (Galimberti et al. 2014).

All the required information to estimate the vibration modes, such as IR intensities, force constants, reduced masses, and so on, exists in the output of the Gaussian calculation.

To compute the Debye temperature (θ), the highest frequency associated with skeletal vibration mode should be chosen. According to the definition of skeletal vibration, we need to find the frequency with the maximum contribution of the backbone atoms during the vibration and the highest Infrared (IR) intensities to discover the highest skeletal vibration frequency. Eq. (2) is used to calculate Debye temperature from skeletal frequency (ϑ_1). On the other hand, the group vibrations frequencies (ϑ_E) are determined by vibrational spectra for each molecular unit, using the same output of Gaussian 16. Then, the Einstein temperature is determined with Eq. (3).

$$\theta_1 = \frac{h\vartheta_1}{k} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Debye temperature (θ_1) is associated with the highest frequency of the density of the vibrational states. Regarding Eq. (2) ϑ_1 represents the highest frequency of the vibrational states' density, and h and k are Plank's ($6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ J·s) and Boltzmann's (1.380649×10^{-23} J/K) constants, respectively. Group vibration frequency (ϑ_E), which can be determined with the Infrared (IR) absorption and Raman scattering spectrum, was used to calculate the Einstein temperature (θ_E) by Eq. (3).

$$\theta_E = \frac{h\vartheta_E}{k} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

With the assistance of input parameters in GIM method, some physical features, such as heat capacity, thermal expansion, and glass transition temperature, among others, can be calculated (Ali and Rahaman 2018; Yokota and Tsukushi 2020).

2.2. Group Interaction Modelling: Property prediction

Heat capacity is a principal parameter of the materials in the case of the thermodynamic property's evaluation because the entropy and the enthalpy can be calculated with this parameter. Also, a profound investigation of this property which reflects molecular motion, reveals critical data about the vibrational state of molecules (Nishiyama, Yokota, and Tsukushi 2021; Yokota et al. 2020).

For calculating heat capacity in the constant pressure ($C_{p, cal}$), the Einstein and Debye models were used to calculate the heat capacity at the constant volume. The value of $C_{p, cal}$ was calculated by Eq. (4), which $C_{V, group}$ is the heat capacity contributed by group vibration. $C_{V, skeletal}$ is heat capacity contributed by skeletal vibrations.

$$C_{p, cal} = C_{V, group} + C_{V, skeletal} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

$C_{V, skeletal}$, and $C_{V, group}$ represent the heat capacity at the constant volume and are calculated by Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) (Czerniecka-Kubicka et al. 2015; Nishiyama, Yokota, and Tsukushi 2021; Roles and Wunderlich, n.d.; Roles, Xenopoulos, and Wunderlich 1993; M. Pyda, Bartkowiak, and Wunderlich 1998; M Pyda et al. 1998; M. Pyda, Bopp, and Wunderlich 2004; Thybring 2014; Marek Pyda et al. 2019).

$$C_{V, skeletal} = N_{sk}R \frac{\left(\frac{6.7T}{\theta_1}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{6.7T}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

$$C_{V, group} = N_{group}R \frac{\left(\frac{\theta_E}{T}\right)^2 \exp\left(\frac{\theta_E}{T}\right)}{\left(\exp\left(\frac{\theta_E}{T}\right) - 1\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

The parameter N_{sk} in Eq. (5) indicates the number of skeletal vibrations and was used to assign the heat capacity contributed by skeletal vibrations, N_{group} indicates the number of

group vibrations, and R is the universal constant of gas. N is the number of atoms in the monomer, and $3N$ is the total number of vibrational degrees of freedom. The equation below describes the relations of N , N_{skeletal} , and N_{group} (Czerniecka-Kubicka et al. 2015; Nishiyama, Yokota, and Tsukushi 2021; Roles and Wunderlich, n.d.; Roles, Xenopoulos, and Wunderlich 1993; M. Pyda, Bartkowiak, and Wunderlich 1998; M Pyda et al. 1998; M. Pyda, Bopp, and Wunderlich 2004; Thybring 2014; Marek Pyda et al. 2019).

$$3N = N_{\text{group}} + N_{\text{skeletal}} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

As a principal transition in polymers, the glass transition temperature can affect the other physical performance of polymers. Although polymers have glassy behavior before the T_g , above the T_g they are in the rubbery state (Domínguez 2018). The GIM method (Eq. (8)) can be used to determine the T_g , and all the required input parameters, except Debye temperature, can be calculated with the group contribution method (Joel P. Foreman et al. 2008). In the Equation below, the applied strain rate (r) is assumed to be equal to the angular frequency of 1 Hz in all the calculations of this study.

$$T_g = 0.224 \theta_1 + \frac{0.0513E_{\text{coh}}}{N} - 50 + \frac{1280 + 50\ln\theta_1}{\ln\left(\frac{2\pi\theta_1}{r}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

The coefficient of linear thermal expansion is an essential parameter and is defined as an alteration in dimension as a function of temperature. This parameter significantly affects the structural and mechanical design of materials. As it is revealed in Eq. (9), the linear thermal expansion coefficient depends on the skeletal heat capacity and cohesive energy (Joel P. Foreman et al. 2010; M. Wang, Liao, and Chen 2013).

$$\alpha = \frac{1.38 C_{V, \text{skeletal}}}{3RE_{\text{coh}}} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

As mentioned before, using a set of equations in the GIM method, it is possible to progressively predict the mechanical properties of materials. B_{gam} represents the bulk modulus of the polymers in the glassy states and can be calculated by Eq. (10). Similarly, the bulk modulus (B) can be predicted with Eq. (11).

$$B_{gam} = 5.68 \frac{E_{coh}}{V_W} \times 10^6 \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

$$B(T) = B_{gam} \left(1 - \left(0.1 + \frac{0.09}{\frac{0.48 \times \theta_1 M S}{10^5 L B_{gam}} - 0.9} \right) \int_0^T 0.0067 \exp \left[\frac{-(T - T_g)^2}{2S^2} \right] dT \right) \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

Where S is the width of the Gaussian function of loss peak (S) and is calculated by Eq. (12).

$$S = 6 \left[\frac{1280 + 50 \ln \theta_1}{50 \ln \left(\frac{2\pi \theta_1}{r} \right)} \right]^2 \quad \text{Eq. (12)}$$

The bulk modulus defined in Eq. (11) was used to predict the tensile modulus (E) by Eq. (13). Where $\tan \Delta_g$ is the cumulative loss tangent for the glass transition, calculated by Eq. (14).

$$E = \frac{B(T)}{(1 + \tan \Delta_g)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (13)}$$

$$\tan \Delta_g = 0.0085 \frac{E_{coh}}{N_c} \quad \text{Eq. (14)}$$

With the combination of the bulk modulus and elastic modulus, the Poisson's ratio (ν) can be predicted by Eq.(15) Porter and Gould 2009; Joel P. Foreman et al. 2010; Guest et al. 2013).

$$\nu = 0.5 \left(1 - \frac{E}{3B} \right) \quad \text{Eq. (15)}$$

2.3. Machine learning: Dataset and Descriptors

The Machine learning method consists four main steps: (1) selecting the data, (2) calculating the relevant descriptors, (3) building and training the model, and (4) evaluating the performance of the model.

We have investigated six machine learning models to predict six different properties: Debye temperature (θ_1), glass transition temperature (T_g), heat capacity (C_p), elastic modulus (E), linear thermal expansion (α), and Poisson's ratio (ν). In the first step of machine learning, the datasets were gathered from the existing references, as listed in Table 2.

Table 2. List of the machine learning models summarized in the size of the dataset and the corresponding references.

Model	Dataset size	Database
ML_ θ_1	140	(David Porter 1995)
ML_ T_g	394	(J. Brandrup, et al. 2003)
ML_ C_p	135	(JE 2007; Mark, n.d.; Bicerano, n.d.)
ML_ E	35	(Study, n.d.)
ML_ α	293	(JE 2007)
ML_ ν	29	(Otsuka et al. 2011)

In the next step, after collecting the dataset, the corresponding monomers of the polymers is converted to the SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification)

expressions. Table S.1, in support information, illustrates the SMILES representation and experimental values of their properties for some polymers.

Since SMILES strings are created, descriptors for the molecular structure with various computational methods and software tools can be employed (Peerless et al., n.d.). In this study the descriptors were determined by alvaDesc v.2.0.4, Dragon v.7, and RDKit tools. Approximately 14000 molecular descriptors were calculated by the aforementioned tools.

2.4. Machine learning algorithm: Random forest regression

Random Forest (RF) introduced by Breiman and Cutler (Leo Breiman 2001) was employed in this study. There are numerous examples in the literature where the RF method has demonstrated its effectiveness in various predictive tasks (Xiao et al. 2023; Gupta, Schadler, and Sundararaman 2021; Kishino et al. 2023).

This algorithm is based on the decision tree and combines a group of tree predictors (Palmer et al. 2007). Each decision tree is made in the forest by choosing the section from the initial dataset using the bootstrap method and electing the random number of all variables in each decision node. We used the RandomForestRegressor class from the sklearn.ensemble library in Python (Balcio 2020) to train the Random Forests for solving regression problems.

As a rule, the whole dataset was divided into two main subsets randomly. The training set, the first subset, is 85% of the entire dataset, and the Test set contains the rest of the dataset. For this reason, we used the grid search method to optimize the best hyperparameters with 5-fold cross-validation (CV).

In the prediction model, the number of the tree in the forest ($n_estimators$), the maximum depth of the tree (max_depth), the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node ($min_samples_split$), the minimum number of samples required to be at a leaf node ($min_samples_leaf$), the number of features to consider when looking for the best split ($max_features$) were fixed as hyperparameters (Sun et al. 2020; G 2020). The optimized hyperparameters of each ML model are represented in Table S.2 in support information.

Two statistics were calculated to validate and test the developed models made with the RF method: the squared correlation coefficient (R^2), and the Mean-Absolut-Error (MAE). It is possible to calculate R^2 and MAE by Eq. (16) and Eq. (17), respectively (E Alpaydin 2009; Ça 2019)(Le 2020; E Alpaydin 2009).

$$R = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (y_{0,j} - \bar{y})(y_{p,j} - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (y_{0,j} - \bar{y})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (y_{p,j} - \bar{y})^2}} \quad \text{Eq. (16)}$$

Where N , $y_{0,j}$, y_p and \bar{y} are the number of observations, measured values, predicted, and mean predicted values of the properties, respectively ($j= 1: N$). In the case of the MAE

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_0 - y_p| \quad \text{Eq. (17)}$$

3. Results and discussion

The current research strategy is comprised of three main steps. Firstly, the GIM method was utilized to calculate the thermophysical and mechanical properties of 114 different

polymers. Secondly, six different ML models were constructed to predict the properties of these polymers. Finally, a comparison of the two models was performed to validate their selection and performance against experimental approaches.

3.1. Group interaction modeling results

To predict the properties with GIM method, the input parameters introduced in the Method and Methodology section must be calculated. Table 3 gives a list of the GIM parameter values for several example polymers polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), polyether ether ketone (PEEK), and polybutene (PB-1)). The length of the monomer was calculated using the Avogadro program, and other input parameters (E_{coh} , V_w , N , N_c , and M) are calculated with the group contribution method.

Table 3. Input parameters of six selected polymers

Polymer	Length (Å)	E_{coh} (J/mol)	V_w (cc/mol)	N	N_c	M (g/mol)
PE	2.2	9000	20.5	4	4	28.0313
PP	2.4	13500	30.7	6	6	42.04695
PVA	2.5	22000	25.2	6	6	44.02621
PVDF	2.3	18000	20.46	4	4	64.01246
PEEK	17.1	105100	151.72	17	80	294.277
PB-1	2.6	18000	40.9	7	8	56.1

Vibrational spectroscopy of the polymer's monomer simulated in the gas phase has been used to estimate Debye temperature and Einstein temperature, which are input parameters of GIM method.

Table 4 shows the Debye temperature for several polymers in a range of 200 K to 600 K. The reference values of θ_1 from the book of David Porter (θ_{1_Porter}) are compared with the calculated ones. The calculated values are sorted in column 3 ($\theta_{1_simulation}$), and the error versus the reference values are in column 4. Although the calculated θ follows the reference behavior, the discrepancies between the reference values (θ_{1_Porter}) and the computed using electronic simulations ($\theta_{1_simulation}$) are noteworthy. Table 4 also includes the Debye temperature calculated with machine learning and the error versus the reference values. The following section analyzes the results of machine learning.

Table 4. Compare Debye temperature predicted by ML and Debye temperature calculated by Gaussian.

Polymer	θ_{1_Porter}	$\theta_{1_simulation}$	%Error (Gaussian, Porter)	θ_{1_ML}	%Error (ML, Porter)
PE	316	344	8.8	380	20.2
PP	449	434	3.3	429	4.4
PVA	439	422	3.8	400	8.8
PVDF	209	227	8.6	261	24.8
PEEK	550	469	14.7	475	13.6
PB-1	389	394	1.2	374	3.8
Poly (ethylene isophthalate)	550	520	5.4	488	11.2

Poly (bisphenol-A terephthalate)	550	516	6.1	506	8
Poly (oxy-m-phenylene)	550	588	6.9	533	3.09
Poly (methyl-p-xylylene)	550	519	5.6	536	2.5
Poly (cyano-p-xylylene)	550	570	3.6	541	1.6
Poly (p-xylylene)	550	532	3.2	498	9.4
Poly (phenylene sulfide)	550	591	7.4	476	13.4
Poly (m-phenylene isophthalate)	550	576	4.7	535	2.7
Poly (oxy (2,6-dimethyl-1,4- phenylene))	550	552	0.3	496	9.8

The input parameters of GIM method shown in Table 3 are complemented with the calculated Debye temperature θ_1 . Therefore, the polymers' thermal properties and mechanical behavior have been analyzed by Eq. (4) - Eq. (14) as a function of temperature using GIM method. The calculated values of glass transition temperature, heat capacity at constant pressure, elastic modulus, linear thermal expansion, and Poisson's ratio for the several instance polymers are listed in Table 5. These properties have been calculated for a given temperature.

Table 5. The properties of the selected polymers using GIM method with θ_1 from simulation method

Polymer	T_g (K)	C_p (J/mol K)	E (MPa)	α [10^{-6} 1/K]	ν
PE	221.3	64	1208	130	0.418
PP	241.6	70	1207	193.51	0.418
PVA	329.6	72	2479	276	0.41

PVDF	243.2	85	1627	245	0.43
PEEK	501.5	371	2669	360	0.47
PB-1	253.1	105	283	155	0.47

3.2. Machine learning results

The machine learning approach has been implemented and tested in 6 different models, on model per polymer property. At the beginning, abundant number of descriptors were used to build the primary RF models. However, to increase the model's performance, an importance features analysis has been used to extract the more important and relevant descriptors and exclude the irrelevant ones. This analysis has been applied to all six machine learning models. After analyzing and finding the most relevant and important descriptors, new RF models were built to make the prediction. For this purpose, top descriptors from the importance features technique have been selected, and the latest forecast has been done. Table 6 shows the material properties of six selected polymers calculated using the described ML models. These results are in good agreement with measured values for the selected polymers.

Table 6. The properties of the selected polymers using ML method

Polymer	T _g (K)	C _p (J/mol. K)	E (Mpa)	α [10^{-6} 1/K]	ν
PE	236	40.8	1140	107.137	0,459
PP	259	65.4	1065	205.45	0.4203
PVA	323	68.2	2733	226.99	0.3836
PVDF	258	76	1477	279.2	0.3646
PEEK	387	325	2239	380.03	0.4119

the performance of six RF models, each with selected descriptors, and sorted their squared correlation coefficient of the training set ($R^2_{\text{train set}}$) and test set ($R^2_{\text{test set}}$), and MAE are analyzed in Table 7. A low MAE and the high value of the R^2 correspond to the high accuracy of the model. R^2 of the train set ranges from 0.83 to 0.958, and R^2 of the test set ranges from 0.85 to 0.967. The model for the elastic modulus (ML_E) has the lowest value of R^2 of the test set, 0.85 for the given property. On the contrary, the model for the heat capacity, ML_C_p, performs better than the other five models, with a mean absolute error of 12.1 J/mol. K and R^2 of the test set of 0.965.

Table 7. Performance of each RF model

Predicted Parameters	$R^2_{\text{train set}}$	$R^2_{\text{test set}}$	MAE
ML_ θ_1	0.95	0.934	18.6 K
ML_ T _g	0.93	0.83	13.1 K
ML_ C _p	0.965	0.955	12.1 J/mol. K
ML_ E	0.85	0.84	229 MPa
ML_ α	0.91	0.90	2.1×10^{-5} [1/°C]
ML_ ν	0.92	0.91	0.0086

In Fig. 1 the predicted values of various material properties using the RF method are compared to the expected (experimental) values for both the training and test sets. For Debye temperature (Fig. 1a), most of the predicted values are close to the expected values, except for a few outliers at 550 K.

The expected values for Debye temperature were obtained from David Porter's book, with a value of θ_D estimated at 550 K for polymers containing phenyl rings (Joel P. Foreman et al. 2010). Hence, the deviation of the model at 550 K is more significant than other temperatures, resulting in some data points deviating from the diagonal line on the plot.

For glass transition temperature (Fig. 1b), the blue points representing the training set are closer to the expected = predicted line than the black points representing the test set. However, for heat capacity, linear thermal expansion, and Poisson ratio (Fig. 1c, e, and f), most data points lie on the expected = predicted line, indicating good agreement between predicted and expected values. In contrast, for elastic modulus (Fig. 1d), both the training and test set data points are scattered compared to the other five plots.

The insets of Fig.1 display the histogram of the MAE distribution for each model. The mean absolute error histogram is a way to show the comparative forecasting performance. A model with higher accuracy will have a higher density of errors in the center of the histogram (MAE=0) and a lower error rate overall. Based on the results, the six RF models can predict material properties from chemical structures with reasonable accuracy, making them useful for predicting the behavior of new materials.

Fig.1 Expected vs. predicted values of a) Debye temperature, b) glass transition temperature, c) heat capacity, d) Elastic modulus, e) linear thermal expansion, f) Poisson ratio, and the distribution of MAE of each RF model.

As mentioned above, the important feature analysis is used to determine the relative importance of descriptors in predicting the target variable in model. It helps to identify the features that have the most influence on the model's predictions.

The plot of important descriptors and their corresponding importance scores is provided in Fig.S.1 in support information. This plot visually represents the relative importance of each feature in predicting the target variable. Moreover, the number and name of the applied descriptors for each ML model are listed in Table 8. In the model to predict Debye temperature θ_D , five Continuous and Data-Driven Descriptors (CDDD) descriptors are used. CDDD descriptors are molecular structure descriptors that offer a unique, compact, and continuous vector representation for each compound (Article, Winter, and Montanari 2018).

“ChiA” descriptors as 2D matrix-based descriptors for prediction T_g reflect information about interatomic distances, bond distances, ring types, planar and non-planar systems, and atom types. A small “ChiA” indicates a small interatomic distance, which results in a low degree of freedom for rotation and leads to high T_g (Yu and Huang 2017). The third important descriptor for ML_ T_g model is the rotatable bond fraction (RBF). The number of rotatable bonds, which shows the stiffness of the chain can affect the T_g , and a larger number of rotatable bonds will have a lower T_g . Also, SpMax_EA is an edge adjacency index derived from the H-depleted molecular graph and encodes the connectivity between graph edges. This descriptor leads to eigenvalue from the edge adjacency matrix weighted by bond order and reflects molecular shape (Yu and Huang 2017). GATS1v, as a 2D autocorrelations descriptor, encodes the relative position of atoms or atom properties by calculating the separation between atom pairs in terms of the number of bonds (Sliwoski, Mendenhall, and Meiler 2016). Although a variety of factors affect the glass transition temperature of the polymers, rigidity and stiffness are important factors related to this property. Thus, these five descriptors can predict glass transition sufficiently (Yu and Huang 2017).

SA_{tot}, as a molecular descriptor, presents the total surface area (Sebenji, Sakac, and Poša 2014). The relation between the surface area and heat capacity C_p is obvious. Moreover, “Autocorr3d” descriptors exist in important descriptor list of RF_ C_p , ML_ E , and ML_ α models. These descriptors capture the patterns and relationships between atoms at different distances and orientations. These patterns can be indicative of the molecular characteristics, and provide important 3D-structural information and translate the relative position of atoms to the atom properties (Sliwoski, Mendenhall, and Meiler 2016). From a physical perspective, it is not easy to explain the exact effect of these descriptors on the properties. However, it is obvious that the position of the atoms has an extreme effect on the thermodynamic properties of the polymers, such as heat capacity, elastic modulus, and linear thermal expansion.

SpMAD_ $B(s)$ as a 2D matrix-based descriptor shows the spectral mean absolute deviation from Burden matrix. The given information of Burden matrix (atomic number of the atoms, type of the bonds, ...) is useful information that can affect the molecules' mechanical behavior for prediction of the elastic modulus E . TDB04i is a 3D Topological distance-based descriptor and is the third important descriptor in ML_ E model (Kowalewski and Ray 2020). These topological distance-based descriptors contain significant structural relations like conformation information. The conformation and crystallinity of polymers influence mechanical properties as well as modulus, as a more ordered and crystalline structure generally leads to a higher modulus, while a less ordered and amorphous structure typically results in a lower modulus.

R3m+ relates the maximal autocorrelation of lag 3 divided by mass and Psi_ e_{1d} , is a 1D descriptor that belongs to the family of electrotopological state indices (Sestraș, Jäntschi,

and Bolboacă 2012). These features are related to the molecular size, shape, and electronic properties of the polymer chains. Elastic modulus (E) is a measure of a material's stiffness and its ability to resist deformation under stress. It is influenced by the size, shape, and electronic properties of the polymer chains. Therefore, descriptors that capture these characteristics are critical for accurately predicting E.

Table 8 reveals that the linear thermal expansion model relies on five descriptors, where the Weighted Holistic Invariant Molecular (WHIM) is the most influential. The WHIM descriptor encodes information about size, shape, symmetry, and atom distribution from the atomic coordinates. Additionally, GETAWAY (GEometry, Topology, and Atom-Weights Assembly) descriptors emerge as significant features in both ML_α and ML_v. Furthermore, Gmax is the maximum geometrical distance between the atoms, and MAXDP is the Maximum positive difference between the intrinsic states of the atoms of a molecule, are also among the important descriptors (Rinaldo, Ce, and Melo 2014). For the ML_α model, geometrical and topological factors, flexibility and stiffness of the bonds, and cohesive forces between molecules are considered the principal parameters (Gracheva et al. 2021).

GATS1p, Mor11m, and getaway188 are used to build the final version of the ML_v model. Mor11m reflects the three-dimensional structure of the polymers which is relevant in understanding their mechanical properties such as Poisson ratio (Faghihi et al. 2019). GATS1p is a descriptor that takes into account the polarizability of molecules (Descriptors 2020), which is an important factor in determining the intermolecular forces that affect Poisson ratio. Lastly, getaway188 is a descriptor that considers the geometrical and topological factors of molecules, which also play a crucial role in determining Poisson ratio. By incorporating these descriptors into the ML model, it can better capture

the complex relationships between the molecular structure and Poisson ratio, leading to more accurate predictions.

Table 8. Name and number of the descriptors in each ML model

Model	Number of descriptors	Descriptors
ML_ θ_1	5	CDDD ¹ _185, 198, 241, 297, 463
ML_ T_g	6	ChiA_B (p, v), RBF, SpMAX_EA, GATS1v
ML_ C_p	3	SA _{tot} , autocorr3d36, 3d 66
ML_ E	5	autocorr3d12, SpMAD_B(s), TDB04i, R3m+, Psi_e_1d
ML_ α	5	whim99, getaway41, Gmax, autocorr3d55, MAXDP
ML_ v	3	GATS1p, Mor11m, getaway188

3.3. Comparison ML and GIM results

Machine learning and group contribution methods offer different approaches for predicting properties of polymers. ML leverages data-driven models and algorithms to learn complex patterns and relationships between molecular features and properties. It can capture non-linear relationships and adapt to various polymer systems, making it suitable for predicting a wide range of properties. ML methods require large datasets for training and may exhibit high accuracy if trained on diverse and representative data.

¹ Continuous and Data-Driven Descriptors

On the other hand, group contribution methods utilize predefined rules or parameters derived from empirical data. These methods simplify the prediction process by breaking down the polymer structure into functional groups or fragments and estimating the contributions of these groups to the overall property. Group contribution methods are typically based on empirical correlations and can provide quick estimates of properties with limited data. However, they may have limitations in capturing the complexity and subtle variations in polymer systems, leading to lower prediction accuracy compared to ML approaches.

The Debye temperature is estimated using Gaussian16 software for electronic structure calculations, and ML models for several polymers have been compared in Table 4. The values from the book of Porter are used as a reference to compute the error of the calculated values. Notably, the values calculated via Gaussian16 software in gas phase show better accuracy than those calculated with ML models. Because the Debye temperature is an input parameter for GIM method, the predicted properties by GIM method can be calculated considering the Debye temperature from electronic structure calculations or ML models.

Fig. 2 presents the percentage error of each method compared with experimental values (Table S.2). %Error (ML) is the percentage error of the ML prediction for each property. %Error (GIM/ θ_1 from ML) and %Error (GIM/ θ_1 from simulation) are the calculated values of properties which contributed to finding the error come from GIM model. The difference between “GIM/ θ_1 from ML” and “GIM/ θ_1 from simulation” is that Debye temperature in the first model is predicted by ML, but in the second model is computed by Gaussian software (electronic simulation method).

By comparing the errors of Fig. 2, generally, ML technique can predict the properties better than the other two GIM methods. ML is extracting the relation of the properties and chemical structure. In simple words, ML was trained by patterns and relationships from large data sets. ML has discovered the complex connection between the input (descriptors) and the output (predicted properties) and inferred it by a fit model for each single data set. Chemical structure dictates the properties of the polymers, and the ML model can learn to associate them with each other without considering any semi-empirical or analytical model. The drawback of the ML models is the needed amount of experimental data and defining the relevant descriptors.

By considering the percentage error of the linear thermal expansion, Poisson's ratio and elastic modulus of GIM/ θ_1 from ML and GIM/ θ_1 from simulation models are close between them. Hence, we conclude that these properties are less sensitive to θ_1 .

However, the influence and effect of θ_1 on glass transition temperature calculated by Eq. (8) are significant.

Fig.2. Error percentage of different polymers for a) Debye temperature, b) glass transition temperature, c) heat capacity, d) Elastic modulus, e) linear thermal expansion, f) Poisson ratio calculated by RF and GIM methods.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, two approaches for predicting the properties of polymers based on their atomic and microstructure were evaluated.

The ML approach, using the Random Forest algorithm, accurately predicted several properties, including Debye temperature, glass transition temperature, heat capacity, elastic modulus, linear thermal expansion, and Poisson's ratio. The model used less than five molecular descriptors, each of which had physical relevance to the predicted properties. The best performing model achieved a high accuracy in predicting heat capacity, with an R^2 value of 0.955 and a low mean absolute error (MAE) of 12.1 J/mol K. However, in contrast, the worst performing model was observed for elastic modulus prediction, exhibiting an R^2 value of 0.84 and a relatively higher MAE of 229 MPa.

In comparison, the GIM method accurately predicted properties for over 114 polymers, including glass transition temperature, heat capacity, elastic modulus, linear thermal expansion, and Poisson's ratio. Among these properties, the method consistently achieved the highest prediction accuracy for T_g , while the prediction performance for linear thermal expansion was comparatively lower. Debye temperature was computed based on IR simulated spectrum. Overall, the ML approach demonstrated higher accuracy levels than the GIM method.

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